

paper Chain

Performance of Circular case 3: Railway
application

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0. Executive summary

The project **PAPERCHAIN, Demo Case 3 - Railway application** aims to demonstrate technical, environmental and economic feasibility of using DPA (deinking paper ash) and DPS (deinking paper sludge) as an alternative back-fill material, instead of the traditional use of virgin - natural gravel or hydraulically bounded products, commonly used behind various retaining wall structures according to Slovenian regulations. The composite from 70 % of DPA and 30 % DPS with the name **MUDIPEL** was used as a **back-fill material set behind a retaining wall structure made from gabions**.

Slovenian paper company VIPAP Videm Krško recycles around 600 Tons of paper per day to produce recycled pulp. The main waste streams from the production are deinking paper sludge (DPS) and paper sludge ash (PSA). Annually, 25.000 Tons of paper sludge ash is produced. Most of it is still dumped in landfills, but in the last few years part of it was used in the cement industry as raw material.

On the other hand, the Slovenian railway infrastructure, which consists of 1207 km of railway lines, needs a lot of material for retaining wall structures near the railway line. In mountainous regions, landslides represent a threat to roads and railways, which need to be prevented by means of expensive actions.

For Circular Case 3 - Railway application, a 50 m long retaining wall was built and almost 100 tonnes of the new composite MUDIPEL was used as a back-fill material behind the retaining wall. The location of the pilot project is in the south of Slovenia, 70 km from VIPAP facilities in Krško.

The handling and supply of the waste for the valorization process optimization was carried out by VIPAP Videm Krško, whereas the technical support and dosage optimization activities were performed by ZAG (Slovenian National Building and Civil Engineering Institute). Slovenian Railways, as the railway operator, supplied all the authorizations, and Dušan Holešek S.P. (SME) was in charge of the construction work.

Long term monitoring showed that the landslide and the retaining wall structure have been stable so far. The performed chemical analyses confirmed that MUDIPEL doesn't entail any negative environmental impact on the water and vegetation above the retaining wall. MUDIPEL also got an STS (Slovenian Technical Approval), which allowed the use of this material as a back-fill material at the construction site.

Pilot structures are a practical example of the use of recycled materials. This way investors, designers and construction companies, who are traditionally reluctant to use new materials in construction, especially recycled materials, can get an insight into the construction technology and the advantages of using recycled materials.

Keywords

Railways	Back-fill material	Deinking paper ash	Deinking paper sludge	Monitoring
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Abbreviations and acronyms:

DPA: Deinking paper ash

DPS: Deinking paper sludge

PPI: Pulp and Paper Industry

QA: Quality Assurance

CC3: Circular Case 3

PSA: Paper Sludge Ash

1. Introduction

The objectives of Circular Case 3 – Railway application is to demonstrate the **use of composite (paper deinking ash and paper deinking sludge), MUDIPEL, as a back-fill material** set behind a retaining wall structure.

Slovenian paper company VIPAP Videm Krško recycles around 600 tonnes of paper per day to produce recycled pulp. Main waste streams from the production are deinking paper sludge (DPS) and paper sludge ash (PSA). Annually, 25.000 tonnes of paper sludge ash are produced. Most of it is still dumped in landfills, but in the last few years a part of it was used in the cement industry as raw material.

On the other hand, the Slovenian railway infrastructure, which consists of 1207 km of railway lines, needs a lot of material for retaining wall structures near the railway line. In mountainous regions, landslides represent a threat to roads and railways, which need to be prevented by means of expensive actions.

For Circular Case 3 - Railway application, a 50 m long retaining wall was built and almost 100 tonnes of the new composite MUDIPEL was used as a back-fill material behind the retaining wall. The retaining wall was built from gabions filled with gravel material. The location of the pilot project is in the south of Slovenia, 70 km from VIPAP facilities in Krško, which was very convenient for the transport of MUDIPEL.

Firstly, a **detailed geomechanical investigation** of the railway zone was carried out with geomechanical laboratory and field tests. Several research boreholes were drilled to determine the depth of the landslide. Based on the geotechnical research the retaining structure design was prepared. The results were published in the following reports:

1. Report No. 297/17-710-2, about geomechanical investigations on landslide Rogovila, ZAG
2. Report No. 059-018-8 Design of the excavation and retaining wall structure, Arping.

Many tests of different composites were performed at **laboratory scale** at the same time. The major critical points identified were: the type of mixing, the time dependent behaviour of the composite, compressive and shear properties of the composite. The results were published in the following reports:

1. Deliverable D4.1: Report on solution feasibility and constraints
2. Report No. 296/17-710-4 about geomechanical laboratory investigation of the composite MUDIPEL, ZAG

Additional field tests were performed to deal with the questions regarding the use of the optimal technology for mixing and compacting the new composite. For this reason **small demo fields** were built at the VIPAP's facility for testing different mixtures of DPA and DPS. The results are published in the reports:

1. Report No. 296/17-710-3 Report about results of the Small demo fields at the VIPAP's facility, ZAG
2. Deliverable D4.2: Demonstration projects setup conditions
3. Report No. P296/17-710-5 Results of laboratory and In-situ controlling test for the landslide Rogovila, ZAG.
4. Report No. 059-018-8 Design of the excavation and retaining wall structure, Arping.

The final decision for the composite to be used was taken on the basis of statistical results of field and laboratory measurements, experience with using the composites for building small test fields and the chemical results of the leakage tests. The composite with 30 % of DPS and 70 % DPA was chosen and named MUDIPEL. Considering the technological possibilities for preparing and installing the composite, the compaction is possible within 4 hours after mixing. Such a composite is solid enough to stabilize the unstable slope and at the same time allows enough deformation that could happen behind the retaining wall structure. The material was mixed at VIPAP's facility and then in an hour and a half transported to the construction site where it was compacted into thin layers of 15 cm.

According to the legislation in Slovenia, a recycled material not covered by an existing harmonized standard shouldn't be used for buildings and infrastructure construction without an STS (**Slovenian Technical Approval**). For recycled materials, the appropriate chemical and mechanical tests need to be performed in order to prove that all the mechanical and environmental requirements for an equivalent natural or artificial material are fulfilled. Through the performance of the laboratory and field tests, STS No. 18/0011 was granted for MUDIPEL, which allowed its use as a back-fill material at the construction site.

Finally, the building of the **retaining wall structure** was started in September 2018. Every installed layer was tested according to the Slovenian Technical specification for back-fill material (TSC 05.413).

Results of the Demo case 3 of the retaining wall, together with the quality control and monitoring results of the first year were presented in following reports:

1. Report No. P296/17-710-5 Results of laboratory and In-situ controlling test for the landslide Rogovila, ZAG.
2. Deliverable D5.3 Implementation of Circular Case 3 Railway applications

The handling and supply of the waste for the valorization process optimization was done by VIPAP Videm Krško, while the technical support and the dosage optimization activities were performed by ZAG (Slovenian National Building and Civil Engineering Institute). Slovenian Railways, as the railway operator, awarded all the required authorizations, and Dušan Holešek S.P. (SME) was in charge of the construction works.

The whole procedure is presented in Figure 1.

FIGURE 1 CONSTRUCTION PROCEDURE FOR THE RETAINING WALL WITH MUDIPEL

1.1. Objectives

The Demo Case 3 of the PAPERCHAIN, Project aims to demonstrate the technical, environmental and economic feasibility of using DPA (deinking paper ash) and DPS (deinking paper sludge) as an alternative back-fill material, instead of the traditional use of virgin gravel or hydraulically bounded products, commonly used behind various retaining wall structures according to Slovenian regulations.

With significant increasing production rates of ash, the pulp and paper industry is intensively seeking energy-efficient mechanisms for ecological and economical ash management. Strict regulations on landfill management have driven the pulp and paper industry to pursue better alternatives for recycling and reusing the generated fly ash.

Sustainable approach in building industry increased the focus on the utilization of paper residues as value-added geomaterials and as cost-effective substitutes for natural components in construction and geotechnical engineering projects.

All over the world, the construction industry is the largest consumer of material resources and consumes up to 50 % of all material resources taken from nature. The continuous extraction of these natural resources, along other negative environmental activities by humans has far-reaching impacts on environmental biodiversity and increases the tendencies of greenhouse effects.

Several studies confirmed that excavation, transportation and processing of the natural resources used in producing natural construction materials and products consume the majority of energy, along with the operational energy, over the entire lifecycle of buildings (Utama et al., 2012; Sartori and Hestnes, 2007; Ramesh et al., 2010; Anink et al., 1996). Similarly, the construction industry accounts for the largest portion of global waste and pollution, up to 30 % of global waste (Ibrahim et al., 2010).

The construction industry does not only have the potential of using its own waste for further construction activities, also several types of domestic waste and postconsumer materials have been used in the production of construction materials (Dunster, 2012). One of the proven means through which waste has been diverted from landfill is through recycling of the waste products. Recent studies on recycling have also focussed on the use of recycled aggregates in various construction activities.

Unfortunately, studies show that recycled materials have been underutilised in construction projects and their acceptance is still low within the construction industry (Mansikkasalo et al., 2014). Although there is a well-established market for recycled concrete as a construction materials (Watts and Partners, 2008), Addis (2006) points out that recycled products are not integrated into large projects as much they could be and are not well undertaken by mainstream contractors, design engineers and architects. Similarly, it is clear that despite the availability of recycled products in construction market, their adoption and market growth is relatively slow (Chick and Micklethwaite, 2004). Unfortunately, no research efforts have been made to determine the impediments to use recycled materials in construction projects.

Despite the low adoption of recycling products in construction projects, governments have only set targets for waste recycling, without any research efforts to identify the barriers to using recycled products.

The aim of Paperchain project – Circular Case 3 (CC3) is to present the use of recycled products in a real scale demo, from laboratory test to a real building structure. Therefore, the objectives of the project are to evaluate the perspectives of construction professionals (designers and contractors) on impediments to have a wide adoption of recycled materials in the industry, as well as strategies that could be adopted to improve the use of recycled products in construction projects. The results from the CC3 would

help policy makers in providing the right platforms to enhance the use of recycled products in construction projects, thereby creating markets for the products.

Pilot structures are a practical example of the use of recycled materials, this way the technology is tested in the construction site. Long-term monitoring of the structure provides an additional guarantee that the structure is safe and stable. It also checks the effects on the environment, such as groundwater and surrounding plants. Investors, designers and construction companies can get an insight into the construction technology and the advantages of using recycled materials in geotechnical structures.

For these reasons, the construction of pilot projects is very important, as it encourages all partners in construction industry to find new solutions for the use of recycled materials in construction field.

1.2. Pilot's location

The Demo structure corresponding to this Circular Case was built in a Slovenian railway, and consisted of a 50 m length test section for landslide prevention. The location of the pilot project is in the south of Slovenia (Figure 2).

FIGURE 2 PILOT PROJECT'S LOCATION

There is an unstable slope in the area near the railway line between Ljubljana and Novo mesto. The landslide was stabilised with a retaining wall structure. The instability of the slope was already evident during the geological-geomechanical mapping of the site. The existing telephone poles along the railway layout were unstable, the road above the slope is severely cracked and individual stone blocks are frequently unstable and inclined towards the railway line (Figure 3).

FIGURE 3 LOCATION BEFORE THE RETAINING WALL CONSTRUCTION

1.1. Construction work

Pilot construction works started in August 2018. Gabions made from iron mesh and gravel material were used for the retaining wall structure, while the recycled material was set as back-fill material behind the retaining wall structure (Figure 4).

FIGURE 4 SKETCH OF THE RETAINING WALL STRUCTURE

The work was divided into the following steps:

- Earth works
- Foundation of the retaining wall
- Building of the first layer of the gabions
- Installing MUDIPEL as the back-fill material (Figure 5, Figure 6)
- Building of the second layer of the gabions
- Installing MUDIPEL as the back-fill material
- Installing the surface drainage system and other surface work like leveling with humus and grass (Figure 7, Figure 8)

A simplified procedure scheme is presented in Figure 5. The layer compaction is showed in Figure 6 and Figure 7. Back- fill material (MUDIPEL) was covered with soil (Figure 8) and greened with vegetation (Figure 9). The finished retaining wall structure is shown in Figure 10 and Figure 11. The results of the in-situ and laboratory control tests are presented in report **No. P296/17-710-5 Results of laboratory and in-situ tests for the landslide Rogovila, ZAG.**

FIGURE 5 PROJECT PHASES FOR CONSTRUCTION WORK OF PILOT STRUCTURE

FIGURE 6 SURFACE OF MUDIPEL LAYER

FIGURE 7 COMPACTION OF MUDIPEL

FIGURE 8 COVER LAYER OF SOIL

FIGURE 9 GREENING OF THE SURFACE

FIGURE 10 RETAINING WALL STRUCTURE

FIGURE 11 WIDER AREA OF RETAINING WALL STRUCTURE

2. Factory production control

One of the major problems with the use of recycled materials is the quality control of waste and waste homogeneity. For this purpose, the control of the quality of PSA is performed, which significantly affects the geomechanical properties of the composite MUDIPEL.

2.1. Raw material

DPA and DPS are residues from deinking paper industry (DPI) VIPAP Videm, Krško. DPA is a burning residue generated in boiler No. 5, where DPS is burnt. DPA consists of slag (approx. 90 % by weight) and fly ash (approx. 10 % by weight). Fly ash is a dust, with a particle size up to 1 mm, while slag consists of grain agglomerates of ash of sizes up to 1 cm. Both chemical and mineralogical compositions are similar. Most of the components are in an amorphous phase. The main crystalline components consist of calcite, lime, portlandite and other minerals in minor quantities.

DPS is generated by waste paper processing through the deinking process at the DIP plant and the industrial waste water treatment plant from the production of paper and municipal waste water from VIPAP.

2.1. Composite MUDIPEL

Based on several geomechanical and chemical analyses, the composition for MUDIPEL was determined as 70 % of DPA and 30 % of DPS by dry mass (Figure 12). The final decision for the composite used was made on the basis of statistical results of field and laboratory measurements, experience with using the composites for building small test fields and the chemical results of the leakage tests. Considering the technological possibilities for preparing and installing the composite, the compaction was possible within 4 hours after mixing. Such a composite is still solid enough to stabilize the unstable slope and at the same time allows enough deformation, which could happen behind the retaining wall structure.

Further characteristics and details of MUDIPEL were presented in Deliverable **D4.1, Report on solution feasibility and constraints**, and in report **ZAG No. 296/17-710-4 Report about geomechanical laboratory investigation of the composite MUDIPEL**.

FIGURE 12 COMPONENT OF THE NEW COMPOSITE MUDIPEL

Mineral composition is presented in Table 1 and in Figure 13. Geomechanical properties of MUDIPEL are presented in Table 2 .

TABLE 1 COMPOSITION OF MUDIPEL

Composition of Mudipel (XRD analysis)			
CaCO_3	Calcite	$(\text{KF})_2(\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3)_3(\text{SiO}_2)_6$	Illite/ muscovite
$\text{Al}_2\text{Si}_2\text{O}_5(\text{OH})_4$	Kaolinite	$\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$	Portlandite
SiO_2	Quartz	$\text{Ca}_4\text{Al}_2\text{O}_6(\text{CO}_3)_{0.5}(\text{OH}) 11\text{H}_2\text{O}$	Hemicarboaluminate
$\text{CaMg}(\text{CO})_3$	Dolomite	$\text{Ca}_4\text{Al}_2\text{O}_6\text{CO}_3 11\text{H}_2\text{O}$	Monocarboaluminate
$\text{Mg}_3\text{Si}_4\text{O}_{10}(\text{OH})_2$	Talc		

FIGURE 13 MINERAL COMPOSITION OF MUDIPEL

TABLE 2 GEOMECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF MUDIPEL

Geomechanical properties		
Optimal Moisture Content, w_{opt} (%)		51
Maximum Dry Density, γ_{dmax} (Mg/m ³)		0,95
Specific Gravity, γ_s (Mg/m ³)		2.25
Uniaxial compression strength after 1 day/28 days, R_c (MPa)	0,47	1,62
Friction angle immediately/after 28 days, ϕ (°)	44	48
Cohesion immediately/after 28 days, c (MPa)	0,04	0,2
Water permeability after 28 days, k (m/s)		$5 \cdot 10^{-10}$
Water absorption after 28 days, w_a (%)		5,5
Dynamic bearing modulus-immediately, E_{vd} (MPa)		10-25

2.2. Deinking paper ash production control

The main influence on MUDIPEL characteristics depends on PSA and were monitored for more than 2 years (March 2018 to December 2020). In this period the following tests were performed:

- particle size distribution
- Proctor test
- unconfined compressive strength
- XRD-mineralogy.

2.2.1. Particle size distribution

The results showed small differences in the percentage of particles above 2 mm and below 0,002 mm. Between these two values the presence of particles differs from one sample to another, but with geomechanical tests it was confirmed that it does not influence the final quality of the product (Figure 14). The average values are presented in Table 3.

FIGURE 14 PARTICLE SIZE DISTRIBUTION FOR PSA

In the middle of year 2018, the filters of VIPAP’s boiler were replaced, but it did not have an impact on the MUDIPEL quality (Figure 15).

FIGURE 15 PARTICLE SIZE PER TAKEN SAMPLES

TABLE 3 NUMERICAL VALUES OF PARTICLE SIZE DISTRIBUTION

	min	max	avg.
Particles under 2,0 mm (%)	93	100	99
Particles under 0,063 mm (%)	53	88	69
Particles under 0,002 mm (%)	6	14	8.9

2.2.2. Optimal water content and maximal dry density (Proctor tests)

Optimal water content and maximal dry density are parameters which have a high impact on the MUDIPEL compaction at the construction site. Results are on average within the limits that were determined in Slovenian Technical Approval (STS) document

for PSA (Figure 16). Limits are presented with the red line. Similar results are for maximal dry density, where only a few samples exceed the limits (Figure 17).

FIGURE 16 OPTIMAL WATER CONTENT FOR PSA

FIGURE 17 MAXIMUM DRY DENSITY FOR PSA

Uniaxial compressive strength is an indicator of how the material binds and what strength develops immediately after mixing. Most samples have an adequate uniaxial

compressive strength (Figure 18) with respect to the Slovenian Technical approval for PSA. Minimum, maximum and average values are presented in Table 4.

FIGURE 18 UNIAXIAL COMPRESSIVE STRENGTH FOR PSA

TABLE 4 VALUES OF TEST RESULTS FOR PSA

	min	max	avg.
Optimal water content (%)	44	54	49
Maximum dry density (Mg/m ³)	0,96	1,10	1,01
Unconfined compressive strength (kPa)	180	720	370

2.2.3. Mineralogical composition

Mineralogical composition of PSA is stable and it does not change significantly with time. Minerals such as calcite, kaolinite, quartz, dolomite, talc, illite/ muscovite and portlandite

are present in samples (Table 5). The main crystalline mineral is calcite which has a high influence on the hydration process. DSA reacts with water which results in the formation of hydration products – different calcium aluminate hydrates.

TABLE 5 MINERAL COMPOSITION OF PSA

	Estimated value [% by mass]		
	min	max	avg.
Glassy phase	32	38	35
Calcite (CaCO ₃)	36	42	38
Portlandite (Ca(OH) ₂)	9	13	10
Lime (CaO)	4	10	7
Gehlenite (Ca ₂ Al ₂ SiO ₇)	3	5	4
Talc (Mg ₃ Si ₄ O ₁₀ (OH) ₂)	< 1	2	< 1
Quartz (SiO ₂)	< 1	< 1	< 1
Dolomite (CaMg(CO) ₃)	< 1	2	< 1
Calcium sulfate (CaSO ₄)	< 1	< 1	< 1
Illite/muscovite (KF) ₂ (Al ₂ O ₃) ₃ (SiO ₂) ₆)	~ 0	~ 0	~ 0

3. Long term monitoring

3.1. Monitoring system

Monitoring of both the construction work and the structure performance after its construction was foreseen in the design phase. For that purpose, both geotechnical and environmental parameters are being controlled according to Slovenian regulations. Results are presented in **Deliverable D 5.3: Implementation of Circular Case 3**. Monitoring started before the retaining wall was finished and has been going on for more than 2 years.

An automatic monitoring station is located at the construction site (Figure 19). Most of the data is automatically recorded and sent to ZAG's office, since an automated system was developed to obtain and monitor the following measurements:

- Weather station – precipitation, temperature
- Inclinometers - water level in the slope
- Probe for water content of back-fill material - MUDIPEL
- Probes for temperatures in backfill material – MUDIPEL.

FIGURE 19 MONITORING SYSTEM

3.1. Results of long term monitoring

3.1.1. Displacement monitoring

The displacements that may occur above the retaining wall structure are monitored with a manual inclinometer in boreholes P-7, P-8 and P-9 (Figure 20). Measurements in inclinometer P-7 which is outside the retaining wall structure showed that horizontal deformations continue (Figure 21). The depth of the landslide shear plane is of 8 m. The inclinometers above the retaining wall (P8 and P9) showed that the slope above the retaining wall is stable (Figure 22, Figure 23).

FIGURE 20 LOCATION OF BOREHOLES

FIGURE 21 HORIZONTAL DISPLACEMENTS IN BOREHOLE P6

FIGURE 22 HORIZONTAL DISPLACEMENTS IN BOREHOLE P7

FIGURE 23 HORIZONTAL DISPLACEMENTS IN BOREHOLE P8

3.1.2. Water level

In piezometers P7, P8 and P9 ground water level is measured automatically. During the construction it was considered evident that the water level in the region is below the structure. The water in the boreholes comes from a local inflow into the boreholes and doesn't seep through the soil (Figure 24). Also precipitation does not influence the groundwater level. The results showed that underground water does not have an impact on the stability of the retaining wall.

FIGURE 24 WATER LEVEL IN BOREHOLES

3.1.1. Water content in MUDIPEL

A probe for measuring the moisture content and temperature of the back-fill material (MUDIPEL) was installed below the surface (90 cm), as shown in Figure 25, Figure 26 and Figure 27.

The data is shown in Figure 28. Unfortunately, the automated monitoring system for the water content measurements hadn't started until 2019. The water content at the time of

compaction of the back-fill material was 57 % and currently is around 47 %. The water content of MUDIPEL at compaction was higher than the optimal, which was necessary because part of the water content was used in the chemical reaction. The comparison with the precipitation showed that the material is impermeable, because there is no correlation between the water content and precipitation.

FIGURE 25 LOCATION OF THE PROBE IN MUDIPEL

FIGURE 26 PROBE IN MUDIPEL

FIGURE 27 LOCATION OF THE AUTOMATED SYSTEM FOR THE PROBE

FIGURE 28 WATER CONTENT IN MUDIPEL VS PRECIPITATION

3.1.1.1. Temperature measurement

Temperature is another automatically measured parameter. Measurements are taken at different points and heights of the MUDIPEL, as shown in Figure 29:

- T...at the weather station
- T1...50 cm under the surface of MUDIPEL
- T2...80 cm under the surface of MUDIPEL
- T3...110 cm under the surface of MUDIPEL
- T4...90 cm under the surface of MUDIPEL (temperature sensor in the moisture probe).

FIGURE 29 LOCATION OF THE TEMPERATURE PROBES IN BACK-FILL MATERIAL MUDIPEL

The results of the measurements showed that the daily changes of the outside temperature don't influence the temperature inside the back-fill material significantly (Figure 30). Some correlation can be observed in T1 which is the highest sensor, while the temperatures in T2 and T3 remain quite stable, despite the fluctuation of the outside temperature (Figure 31). But the seasonal change of the temperature is seen clearly from the results.

FIGURE 30 DETAIL RESULTS OF TEMPERATURE MEASUREMENTS FROM 1.9.2019 TO 16.10.2019

FIGURE 31 RESULTS OF THE TEMPERATURE OUTSIDE AND IN MUDIPEL

3.1.1. Geodetic monitoring

Laser scanner measurements were used for detailed geodetical monitoring of the retaining wall structure and the road above the landslide. The geodetic situation before the building is presented in Figure 32 and Figure 33 shows a picture of the final retaining wall.

FIGURE 32 SITUATION BEFORE THE RETAINING WALL CONSTRUCTION

FIGURE 33 SITUATION WITH THE RETAINING WALL STRUCTURE

In the year 2020 we continue with the monitoring of the retaining wall deformations. Measuring with the laser scanner is shown in Figure 34 and its results in Figure 35.

FIGURE 34 MEASURING OF THE RETAINING WALL WITH LASER SCANNER

FIGURE 35 SCANNED SITUATION OF THE RETAINING WALL

FIGURE 36 DEFORMATIONS OF THE STRUCTURE

Detailed deformations of the gabions and foundation are controlled with the laser scanning measurements. The retaining wall is stable with deformations below the measurement error. Deformations only happen in the drainage system where the settlements are less than 5 mm (Figure 36). Drainage system will be fixed in the next months.

Above the retaining wall is a local road (Figure 37) which is fissured and damaged because of the landslide movement. The measurements showed that the deformations still progress in the part of the road where the slope is not supported with the retaining wall structure (Figure 38).

FIGURE 37 SCANNED LOCAL ROAD

FIGURE 38 SCANNED FISSURES IN THE ROAD

3.1.2. Environmental monitoring

The first drainage system was installed between the back-fill material behind the retaining wall and the landslide slope. This way there is no additional water pressure on the structure. Under the back-fill material – MUDIPEL the second drainage system was installed for collecting eluates from MUDIPEL that drain into a plastic tank (Figure 39). Water from the plastic tank and from the near borehole P7 was taken for chemical analyses. Other surface water is drained into the concrete shaft (Figure 40).

These results show that the back-fill material - MUDIPEL doesn't have a significant influence on the water quality, since none of the tested parameters' concentration exceeds the limits set by Slovenian legislation (Table 6).

TABLE 6 RESULTS OF THE CHEMICAL ANALYSIS OF THE WATER FROM THE DRAINAGE SYSTEM

Component	Limit (UR RS No. 98/15)	Surface water in P6 30.8.2018	Water sample 12.4.2019	Water sample 21.5.2019	Water sample 7.10.2019	Water sample 2.6.2020	Water sample 12.11.2020
	mg/l						
As	0,1	0,00074	0,0019	0,0006	0,0017	0,0019	0,0007
Ba	5	0,07	0,0080	0,0073	0,122	0,04	0,063
Cd	0,025	< 0,0002	< 0,0002	< 0,0002	< 0,0002	< 0,0002	< 0,0002
Cr total	0,5	0,0057	0,0031	0,0010	0,011	0,0015	0,0009
Cu	0,5	0,00098	0,042	0,011	0,013	0,039	0,031
Hg	0,005	< 0,0001	< 0,0001	< 0,0001	< 0,0001	< 0,0001	< 0,0001
Mo	1	0,0013	0,018	0,0024	0,0028	0,028	0,02
Ni	0,5	0,034	0,0011	0,0015	0,0024	0,003	0,0015
Pb	0,5	0,00049	0,0005	0,0006	< 0,0005	< 0,0005	< 0,0005
Sb	0,3	0,00016	0,0039	0,0011	0,0017	0,0036	0,0034
Se	0,6	0,00035	0,0005	< 0,0003	0,0003	0,0003	< 0,0003
Zn	2	0,1	< 0,0005	0,0016	0,0005	0,0015	0,011
Chloride	800	-	5,17	1,52	2,19	11	8
Fluoride	10	< 0,0001	0,264	< 0,10	0,204	0,28	0,35
Sulphates	1000	< 0,00005	19	2	14	< 20	< 20

FIGURE 39 THE PLASTIC TANK

FIGURE 40 SURFACE DRAINAGE SYSTEM

3.1.3. Chemical analysis of flowers and grass

Samples of grass growing on the retaining wall surface (Figure 41, Figure 42) and a meadow in its proximity were collected to carry out a chemical analysis. The results were analysed according to the recommendation for soils and the recommendation for soils for agriculture - animal feed (Ur.L.RS 68/96). Some elements from the meadow had

higher concentration than the grass above the MUDIPEL (Table 7, Table 8). The results of chemical analyses confirmed that MUDIPEL does not have any negative environmental impact.

TABLE 7 RESULTS OF CHEMICAL ANALYSIS OF GRASS AND FLOWERS FROM 5.11.2019 TO 6.7.2020

Component	Lower limit value for ground (Ur.L.RS 68/96)	Recommendation for ground for agriculture (animal feed)	Above Mudipel 5.11.2019	Meadow 5.11.2019	Above Mudipel 6.7.2020	Meadow 6.7.2020
mg/kg d.m.						
As			3	0,9	7,3	1,1
Ba			68	83.4	127	18.8
Cd	1	1,5	1	0,3	3	0,5
Cr total	100	200	59,4	10	72,9	24,7
Cu	60	300	15,1	33,2	16,3	8,7
Mo			4,9	21,7	9,7	25,2
Ni	50	75	18,7	3,8	24,7	7,2
Pb	85	250	3,8	1,2	7,6	1,4
Sb			0,1	0,2	< 0,1	< 0,1
Se			< 3,3	< 3,3	2,9	< 2,0
Zn	200	1200	42,3	49	58,3	97,8
Hg	0,8	1,5	< 0,1	< 0,1	< 0,1	< 0,1
Dry matter (%)			92,8	93,7	94,2	93
S (%)			0,26	0,33	0,18	0,13
Fluoride			90,1	< 50	74,5	< 45

TABLE 8 RESULTS OF CHEMICAL ANALYSIS OF GRASS AND FLOWERS FROM 10.11.2020

Component	Recommen- dation for ground	Recommen- dation for ground for agriculture (animal feed)	Above Mudipel 10.11.2020	Meadow 10.11.2020
	mg/kg d.m.			
As			0,3	2,1
Ba			34	36
Cd	1	1,5	0,5	1,7
Cr total	100	200	6,6	25,2
Cu	60	300	8,7	13
Mo			4,1	3,9
Ni	50	75	2,4	9,1
Pb	85	250	0,5	3,2
Sb			< 0,1	< 0,1
Se			< 2	< 2
Zn	200	1200	43,2	52,1
Hg	0,8	1,5	< 0,1	< 0,1
Dry matter (%)			94,8	94,7
S (%)			0,19	0,2
Fluoride			< 50	< 50

FIGURE 41 GREEN AREA ABOVE MUDIPEL

FIGURE 42 WIDER REGION OF THE RETAINING WALL STRUCTURE

4. Conclusions

The objectives of Circular Case 3 – Railway application is to demonstrate the **use of this composite (paper deinking ash and paper deinking sludge), MUDIPEL, as a back-fill material** set behind a retaining wall structure.

Preliminary tests were performed in ZAG's geomechanical laboratory and the results were later verified with small test fields at VIPAP facilities. The technology for the installation of the material at construction sites was determined based on the results measured at the small test fields.

For Circular Case 3 a 50 m long retaining wall was built and almost 100 tonnes of the new composite MUDIPEL was used as a back-fill material behind the retaining wall. The retaining wall was built with gabions filled with gravel material. At the construction site, the composite was installed in 30 cm thick layers. Each layer was compacted and controlled to reach the optimal moisture and maximum density.

One of the major problems with the use of recycled materials is the quality control of the waste and waste homogeneity. For this purpose, the control of the quality of PSA, which significantly affects the geomechanical properties of the composite MUDIPEL, is performed. The results showed that PSA had a fairly uniform particle size distribution and mineral composition over the observed two-year period. Continuous control during the production, mixing and installation stages of MUDIPEL is necessary in order to get high quality back-fill material.

Before, during and after the construction, landslide stability and environmental monitoring were being performed. The monitoring started even before the retaining wall was built and has continued for more than 2 years now. For that purpose, both geotechnical and environmental parameters are being controlled according to Slovenian regulations.

The automated monitoring station is placed at the construction site. Most of the data is automatically recorded and sent to the ZAG's office, since an automated system was developed to obtain and monitor the following measurements; precipitation, temperature, water level in the slope, water content and temperature of back-fill material – MUDIPEL, deformations of landslide and deformations of retaining wall structure.

Based on the results of long term monitoring it was concluded that:

- The technology for mixing and compacting MUDIPEL in layers/structures was improved at the construction site.
- The use of MUDIPEL improved the stability of the slope.

- MUDIPEL is an impermeable material, it was property determined through laboratory tests trials and was later confirmed with the monitoring system installed in the retaining wall.
- MUDIPEL is also a light-weight material with really high shear strength parameters. It could be a very usefull material in those cases in which the foundaiton of the structure has to be on soft soil.
- No sub zero temperature have been observed during the first year. The influence of cold winter 2020/2021 will show whether the material is frost-resistant, as evidenced by laboratory tests.
- The influence of external temperatures decreases with the depth of the material. Daily change of the temperature does not influence the temperature of the MUDIPEL below the surface.
- Both MUDIPEL and water from drainage system comply with all the environmental requirements set by the law.
- Rainwater doesn't influence the water content of MUDIPEL, which indicates an adequate impermeability of the material.
- No displacements were measured in the retaining wall structure after the construction work.

The pilot retaining wall with MUDIPEL as a back-fill material represents a successful practical example of the use of recycled materials. Through it investors, designers and construction companies, who are traditionally reluctant to use new materials in construction, especially recycled materials, can learn about the construction technology and the advantages of using recycled materials.

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Paperchain Deliverables:

11. Deliverable 2.1: Baseline Report – PPI waste streams valorisation potential.
12. Deliverable 8.1: Report on transition assessment for circular economy processes.
13. Deliverable 4.1: Report on solutions feasibility and constraints.
14. Deliverable 2.2: Quality assurance procedures for the circular model demos.
15. Deliverable D2.3: Raw materials supply scenario
16. Deliverable D4.2: Demonstration projects setup conditions
17. Deliverable D 5.3: Implementation of Circular Case 3

Internal sources:

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